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Classification of Bearing Faults in an Induction Motor Using Statistical Analysis and ANN

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses a method for the classification and diagnosis of bearing fault. In this method a multivariable statistical analysis combined with ANN is used. The fault features are extracted using the statistical approach. The extracted features are used as inputs in neural network for the classification purpose. The results obtained prove that the developed method can reliably diagnose different condition of bearing including healthy condition.

Keywords:- *Fault diagnosis, induction motors, monitoring, bearing fault classification, statistical analysis, ANN*

INTRODUCTION

Induction motors play a vital role in the safe and efficient running of industrial plants and processes. Early detection of fault in motor can save a good amount of time and money. Now days an induction motor has got more importance than any other electrical machine. Induction motors are critical component for electrical utilities and process industries.

Failure of an induction motor can result into shut down of a generating plant or the production line. Lots of studies and surveys have proposed that the main cause of failure of an induction machine is bearing fault. Therefore, a reliable bearing fault diagnosis technique is essentially needed to improve and prevent system performance.

Since last decade or more a substantial amount of work is going on in the field of condition monitoring. For the diagnosis of faults the researchers have proposed various methods. Now days the artificial intelligence techniques are being used by the researchers for the fault detection and condition monitoring. Here follows the summary of such excellent methods for the condition monitoring.

In [1], J. C. García-Prada, C. Castejón, and O. J. Lara have proposed a new condition monitoring technique for detection and classification of bearing faults. They used DWT for the feature extraction and extracted features then used as input to the neural network. With this technique they are able to detect and classify the bearing faults such as inner race, outer race, and the faulty rolling element.

In [2], T. Lindh, J. Ahola, P. Spatenka, A-L Rautiainen given new look to the condition monitoring. They in combine used the statistical analysis with fuzzy logic to automatically detect and classify

the bearing problem. The advantages of the fuzzy logic approach include the possibility to change the linguistic rules into decisions by copying the procedure and thinking of a human analyzer. The rules that include uncertainty and inaccuracy are changed into numbers describing the severity or the probability of a fault. Thus, the prediction of fault became more accurate.

In [3], Jie Liu, Wilson Wang, and Farid Golnaraghi have used the GA based feature optimization technique for the bearing fault diagnostics. In this study, a genetic algorithm (GA) based feature optimization technique is proposed to extract the representative features for bearing fault diagnostics.

Based on a designated fitness function, the GA can eliminate human intervention and automatically formulate the optimal features. Instead of using a thorough and complex search space; the fundamental search base in this work is based on energy distribution ratios from several constituent signals that are processed by the use of discrete wavelet packet (DWP) analysis.

In this paper, classification of bearing fault in an induction motor is done using statistical parameters and ANN. Unlike previous classification of bearing faults; the faults are classified as fault in load side bearing or in the rear side bearing.

VARIOUS AI TECHNIQUES FOR FEATURE EXTRACTIONS [4]

Basically, AI is the study of mental facilities through the use of computational models. It has produced a number of tools since its emergence as a discipline in mid 1950s. The tools are of great practical significance in engineering to solve various complex problems normally requiring human intelligence. The powerful tools among these are expert system (knowledge- based system), FLS,

ANN, Neural-Fuzzy, GA, GA assisted ANN and Support Vector Machines (SVM).

A. Expert System:

The expert system (ES), also known as knowledge-based systems (KBS), is basically computer programs embodying knowledge about a narrow domain for the solution of problems related to that domain. An ES mainly consists of a knowledgebase and an inference mechanism. The knowledge base contains domain knowledge, which may be expressed as any combinations of 'IF-THEN' rules, factual statements, frames, objects, procedures and cases. While the inference mechanism manipulates the stored knowledge to produce solutions.

B. Fuzzy Logic System:

A demerit of ordinary, rule-based ES is that they cannot handle new situations not covered explicitly in their knowledge bases. These ESs cannot give any conclusions in these situations. The FLSs are based on a set of rules. These rules allow the input to be fuzzy, i.e. more like the natural way that human express knowledge [XS]. The use of fuzzy logic can enable ESs to be more practical. The knowledge in an ES employing fuzzy logic can be expressed as fuzzy rules (or qualitative statements). A reasoning procedure, the compositional rule of inference, enable conclusions to be drawn by extrapolation or interpolation from. The qualitative information stored in the knowledge base.

C. Artificial Neural Network:

ANN can capture domain knowledge from examples they can readily handle both continuous and discrete data and have good generalization capability as with fuzzy expert systems. An ANN is a computational model of the brain. ANNs assume that computation is distributed over several simple units called neurons,

which are interconnected and operate in parallel thus known as parallel distributed processing systems or connectionist systems. Implicit knowledge is built into a neural network by training it. Some ANNs can be trained by typical input patterns and the corresponding expected output patterns. The error between the actual and expected outputs is used to strengthen the weights of the connections between the neurons. This type of training is known as supervised training. Some of ANNs are trained in an unsupervised mode, where only the input patterns. are provided during training and the network learns automatically to cluster them in groups with similar features.

D. Genetic Algorithm:

GA is a stochastic optimization procedure inspired by natural evolution. It can yield the global optimum solution in a complex multi-model search space without requiring specific knowledge about the problem to be solved. A genetic or evolutionary algorithm operates on a group or population of chromosomes at a time, iteratively applying genetically based operators such as crossover and mutation to produce fitter populations containing better solution chromosomes.

E. Support Vector Machine:

SVMs are the methods for creating functions from a set of labeled training data. The function can be a classification function (the output is binary: is the input in a category) or the function can be a general regression function. For classification, SVMs operate by finding a hyper surface in the space of possible inputs, which will attempt to split the positive examples from the negative examples.

**ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK:
A BRIEF INTRODUCTION [5,6]**

The application of artificial neural networks to various decision-making,

forecasting and classification problems has gained a lot of attention recently. ANN's are able to learn the relationship among past, present and future variables.

The simplest definition of a neural network, more properly referred to as an 'Artificial' Neural Network (ANN), is provided by the inventor of one of the first neuro computers, Dr. Robert Hecht-Nielsen. He defines a neural network as:

"...a computing system made up of a number of simple, highly interconnected processing elements, which process information by their dynamic state response to external inputs."

An Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is an information-processing paradigm, inspired by biological nervous systems. The basic processing element of neural networks is called artificial neurons or simply neurons. The key element of it is the novel structure of the information processing system. It is composed of a large number of highly interconnected processing elements (neurons) working in union to solve specific problems.

Artificial neural systems function as distributed computing networks. Their most basic characteristic is their architecture. Only some networks provide instantaneous responses. Other networks need time to respond and are characterized by their time-domain behavior, which often referred to as dynamics. Neural network also differ from each other in their learning modes. There are variety of learning rules that establish when and how the connecting weights change. Networks

exhibit different speeds and efficiency of learning. As a result, they also differ in their ability to accurately respond to the cues presented at the input.

ANN always learns by example. An ANN is configured for a specific application, such as pattern recognition or data classification, through a learning process. Learning in biological systems involves adjustments to the synaptic connections that exist between the neurons.

Neural networks are typically organized in layers. Layers are made up of a number of interconnected 'nodes' which contain an '**Activation Function**'. Patterns are presented to the network via the '**Input Layer**', which communicates to one or more '**Hidden Layers**' where the actual processing is done via a system of '**Weighted Connections**'. The hidden layers then link to an 'output layer' where the answer is output as shown in the fig. 1.

The commonest type of artificial neural network consists of three groups or layers of units. a layer of "input" units is connected to a layer of "hidden" units, which is connected to a layer of "output" units. The activity of the input units represents the raw information that is fed into the network. The activity of each hidden unit is determined by the activities of the input units and the weights on the connections between the input and the hidden units. The behavior of the output units depends on the activity of the hidden units and the weights between the hidden and output units.

Fig.1:-Feed-forward Neural network

Feed-forward ANNs allow signals to travel one way only; from input to output. There is no feedback (loops) i.e. the output of any layer does not affect that same layer. Feed-forward ANNs tend to be straight forward networks that associate inputs with outputs. They are extensively used in pattern recognition.

This type of organization is also referred to as bottom-up or top-down. Fig. 1, shows one such typical feed forward network. Feedback networks can have signals traveling in both directions by introducing loops in the network. Feedback architectures are also referred to as interactive or recurrent, although the latter term is often used to denote feedback connections in single-layer organizations.

All learning methods used for adaptive neural networks can be classified into two major categories:

- **Supervised learning**
- **Unsupervised learning**

Supervised learning which incorporates an external teacher, so that each output unit is told what its desired response to input signals ought to be. During the

learning process global information may be required. Paradigms of supervised learning include error-correction learning, reinforcement learning and stochastic learning.

Important issue concerning supervised learning is the problem of error convergence, i.e. the minimization of error between the desired and computed unit values. The aim is to determine a set of weights, which minimizes the error. One well-known method, which is common to many learning paradigms, is the least mean square (LMS) convergence.

Unsupervised learning uses no external teacher and is based upon only local information. It is also referred to as self-organization, in the sense that it self-organizes data presented to the network and detects their emergent collective properties. Paradigms of unsupervised learning are Hebbian learning and competitive learning.

Usually, supervised learning is performed off-line, whereas unsupervised learning is performed on-line. In order to train a neural network to perform some task, we must adjust the weights of each unit in

such a way that the error between the desired output and the actual output is reduced. This process requires that the neural network compute the error derivative of the weights (EW). In other words, it must calculate how the error changes as each weight is increased or decreased slightly. The back propagation algorithm is the most widely used method for determining the EW.

Back propagation is a systematic method for training multi-layer networks. Back

propagation provides a computationally efficient method for changing the weights in a feed forward network, with differentiable activation function units.

The aim of this network is to train the net to achieve a balance between the ability to response correctly to the input pattern that are used for training and the ability to provide good responses to the input that are similar. The training routine may require more iteration to converge.

EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

Fig.2:-Experimental Setup

For the experimentation purpose, mains feed three-phase squirrel cage induction motor of 2 HP, 50 Hz, 440 volts AC supply is used. Mechanical loading arrangement is provided to load the motor. There are two bearings in the motor having numbers 6204 and 6205. The bearing 6204 is rear side bearing and 6205 is on load side.

Experiments on the motor are conducted at different load conditions. As the objective of this study is to decide which bearing i.e. rear side or load side bearing, is defective and causing eccentricity in the motor, five load side bearing and three rear side bearings with different mechanical conditions were used in the experimentation.

❑ Load side bearings are numbered as LN, L0, L1, L2 and L3. Bearing LN is new bearing of standard company without any defect, while condition of L0 is similar to LN, but used age of it is approximately 6-8 months. Used age of L1 is 2.5-3 years and significant play was observed in inner race due to wear in balls. In bearing L2, cracked outer race was observed and used life it is approximately 5-6 years, while L3 is obsolete/scrap bearing, with defects in both outer and inner race. Used life of this bearing was probably 10 years.

❑ Rear side bearings are numbered as RN, R0, and R1. Bearing RN is new bearing of standard company without any defect, while condition of R0 is similar to RN, but used life of it was approximately

6-8 months. Bearing R1 was having the significant play in outer race and estimated used life of 2-3 years. Different experiments were conducted with different combinations of rear side and load side bearings to access the performance of these bearings and its effect on the performance of motor.

Three currents I_a , I_b and I_c were captured using the experimental setup shown in fig. 2. The Tektronix DSO, TPS 2014, with 100 MHz bandwidth and adjustable sampling rate of 1GHz is used to capture the currents. The fluke current transformer of rating 400 mV/A, input range of 0.01-5 Amps AC RMS and frequency range 40 Hz-5KHz are used. Approximately, 500 sets of readings were captured on different load conditions at different mains supply conditions and analyzed for classification of the problem.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Experiments are conducted on newly procured 3-phase mains feed induction motor, manufactured by leading Indian industry. All the three phase currents were captured on different load condition of motor under normal (healthy) and

abnormal condition. Machine was loaded through mechanical arrangement. The sampling frequency was kept 5kHz for cases studied. The captured data sets presented in this paper are of the full load condition.

The finding of study is presented sequentially as below-

CASE I: HEALTHY OPERATING CONDITION

The three phase currents were captured under normal operating conditions of induction motor. In this case, motor was fitted with RN-LN bearings on rear and load side respectively. Fig. 3 shows three phase currents captured under healthy conditions. In DFT analysis of this signal, authors observed 25 Hz and 75 Hz dominant frequency components due uneven loading.

CASE II: ABNORMAL OPERATING CONDITION

The various combinations of rear side and load bearings are considered for study. The possible combinations and type of eccentricity observed by it is tabulated in table (I).

Table 1:-Bearing combinations and observed eccentricity

Sr. No.	Rear and Load Side Bearing Combinations	Type of Eccentricity Observed
1	RN-L0	Static
2	RN-L1	Static
3	RN-L2	Both Static and Dynamic
4	RN-L3	Both Static and Dynamic
5	R0-L0	Static
6	R0-L1	Static
7	R0-L2	Both Static and Dynamic
8	R0-L3	Both Static and Dynamic
9	R1-L0	Static
10	R1-L1	Both Static and Dynamic
11	R1-L2	Both Static and Dynamic
12	R1-L3	Maximum Static

A few photographs taken after the experiment are given in the fig 3(a)-(d), for various combinations of bearings given in table (I).

Fig. 3(a), shows the 30 % static eccentricity (shown by arrow) observed in machine when motor is fitted with bearings R0-L3. It is important to note that L3 is having significant play in inner and

outer race and eccentricity observed is along the load side of rotor.

Fig. 3(b), shows the static and dynamic eccentricity observed at the center of rotor in machine when motor is fitted with bearings R0-L1. In fig. 3(c), for combination R1-L2, static and dynamic eccentricity is observed along the rear side of rotor. Slight static eccentricity was observed in fig. 3(d), for bearings R0-L0.

**Fig.3:-Eccentricity observed for various combinations of bearings
(a) R0-L3 (b) R0-L1 (c) R1-L2 (d) R0-L0**

Fig.4:-3-phase currents captured when machine fitted with RN-LN

Fig.5:-3-phase currents captured when machine fitted with R0-L3

Fig.6:-3-phase currents captured when machine fitted with R0-L1

Fig.7:-3-phase currents captured when machine fitted with R1-L2

Fig.8:- 3-phase currents captured when machine fitted with R0-L0

Fig. 4-8 shows the three-phase currents captured when the machine is fitted with bearings RN-LN, R0-L3, R0-L1, R1-L2, R0-L0 respectively. Even Variations in the currents provides the information of abnormal conditions caused due to these bearing fittings.

However, in some of cases like bearing combinations R0-L0 and R1-L2 (Fig.8 and 7 respectively), the wave shapes of three phase currents are very much similar to currents observed in new bearing fittings (Fig. 4). Hence, conditions of these bearings can not be differentiated by a mere observation of current waveforms. Therefore, a new strategic development is suggested to decide the conditions of the bearings using Artificial Neural Network (ANN).

CASE III: TRAINING OF NEURAL NETWORK

Artificial neural network has the feature extraction ability and hence can be used as diagnosis tool. Here, the following statistical parameters are used as feature extraction parameters and are used as inputs for neural network.

1. **Minimum and Maximum Parameter:** Minimum and Maximum value of current is used as one of differentiating parameters in normal and abnormal condition.

2. **Mean value of Signal:** Mean value of signal x is given by-

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n} \tag{1}$$

3. **Median of Signal:** Median is the middle value of data arranged according to size.

4. **Variance:** The sample variance is the average value of squared deviation from the mean \bar{x} and is defined by the equation (2).

$$S^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n-1} \tag{2}$$

5. **Standard Deviation:** Standard deviation is the square root of variance and is given by(3).

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}} \tag{3}$$

6. **Summation of Signal:** Addition of all sample values is used to differentiate the abnormal and normal conditions.

7. **RMS Value:** RMS value is another useful parameters for signals to differentiate amongst each other.

8. **Kurtosis:** The kurtosis is a measure of sharpness of the peak and is defined as normalized fourth order central moment of the signal divided by fourth power of the standard deviation.

$$K = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \frac{(x_i - \bar{x})^4}{\sigma^4} \quad (4)$$

9. **Energy of Signal:** The energy of signal can be calculated as

$$Ex = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} |x(n)|^2 \quad (5)$$

A three layer feed forward network with backpropagation algorithm was used to perform the desired analysis. More than 20 networks were developed and tested, but still classification problem was not solved with accuracy. The network topology used is as follows-

- ❑ The input layer is constituted by set of 9 neurons, in order to consider eight inputs.
- ❑ The five neurons were selected in hidden layer, the selection optimum

number of hidden neurons is done by training the network with different number of neurons and minimum MSE=0.01 was achieved when 5 neurons are used in hidden layer. In fig. 9, MSE obtained in 5000 epochs, for different numbers of neuron in hidden layer is shown.

- ❑ In output layer, two neurons were used. As supervised learning method was used, the desired output vectors are given in table (II).

Table 2:-Output vector representation for healthy and faulty conditions of bearings

Output Vector	Condition of Bearings
T1=[0 0]	Healthy rear and Load bearing
T2=[0 1]	Healthy rear and Faulty load bearing
T3=[1 0]	Faulty Rear and healthy load bearing
T4=[1 1]	Faulty rear and Load Bearings

- ❑ Gradient Descent algorithm was used to train the network.

After successful training, the network was tested offline, for 20 training data sets. Out of it, network correctly detects the problem for 18 times.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, feed-forward neural network with backpropagation algorithm has been used to identify the status of rear side and load side bearing in the three phase

induction machine. The feature extraction was done through the statistical parameters.

This is very useful for early detection of bearing conditions, as bearing problems is the first stage of major electrical faults in the machine. The proposed strategy was tested on three-phase induction motor and found that, it detect the bearing problem 90% of times quite accurately.

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REFERENCES

1. J. C. García-Prada, C. Castejón, and O. J. Lara, "Incipient Bearing Fault Diagnosis using DWT for Feature Extraction" 12th IFT.MM World Congress, Besancon (France), June 2007.
2. T. Lindh, J. Ahola, P. Spatenka, A-L Rautiainen, "Automatic Bearing Fault Classification Combining Statistical classification and Fuzzy logic.
3. Jie Liu, Wilson Wang, and Farid Golnaraghi, "A GA based Feature Optimization Technique for Bearing Fault Diagnostics." International Journal of computer science and network security, vol.7, No. 9 Sept 2007.
4. Arfat Siddique, Gx Yadava and Bhim Singh, "Application of Artificial Intelligence Technique for Induction Machine Stator Fault diagnostics." Symposium on diagnostics for electric machine, Power electronics and drives. Allandale, GA, USA, August 2003.
5. J. M. Zurada, "Introduction to Artificial Neural System" Jaico Publication House, 6th edition. www.cs.duke.edu/brd/Teaching.
6. William T Thomson and Mark Fenger, "current signature analysis to detect induction motor fault". IEEE Industry Application Magazine, July/August 2001.

Fig. 9:-Effect of neurons in hidden layer on MSE